

EXTRINSIC REWARDS AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

In government ministries there is reported high staff turnover, demoralized and unsatisfied public servants. Thus, the focus on reward schemes as a means to improve performance of the employees. This article focus was on extrinsic rewards and its influence on employee performance. The paper was anchored on expectancy theory and adopted descriptive research design. Secondary data was collected from conducting desk review of published articles and published and peer-reviewed articles were purposively sampled. The findings revealed that extrinsic rewards improved employee performance. The study concluded that extrinsic rewards with constructs of salary and salary increment, bonuses and monetary gifts improved employee performance. The paper recommends to organizations to develop fair, equitable and just reward scheme that will motivate and improve employee performance. There is also need for policies to regulate and guide HR practitioners on handling of rewards for improve employee performance.

KEY WORDS: Extrinsic Rewards, Employee Performance

1.0 Introduction

Success and survival of organizations is largely dependent on the employees, the work environment, practices and systems. When it comes to the employees, they are tasked with delivery of services as per needs of the customers and products as specified by the market and industry. The only way that the employee can deliver is if they are motivated and rewarded for the work they do (Kumari, Ali & Abbas, 2021). As such the organization and its leadership must adopt reward management practices that will motivate employees leading to improve quality of services and products. Mule (2020) confirmed that high performing employees expect to be appreciated, rewarded and recognized by top executive team in the organization. The adopted reward scheme can cover extrinsic or intrinsic rewards, while this article will focus on extrinsic rewards.

1.1.0 Extrinsic Rewards

Extrinsic rewards entail the tangible rewards than an employee receives after meeting set targets and organizational objectives (Manzoor, Wei & Asif, 2021). It may include salary which is a fixed

payment amount given at a specified time in exchange for services provided. There is bonus which can include fixed bonuses or bonuses given as per performance outcomes especially in the case of sales people. The rewards can also include periodic salary raises and monetary gifts like gift cards that build emotional bond between the employee and organization. Noor, Fareed, Isa and Aziz (2018) noted that salaries, salary increment and bonus pay which work to improve the performance of the individual staff and also reflect on the overall organizational outcome. The employer or top manager expects that the reward program positively influences the employee performance and encourage those who are performing poorly to up their game. Additionally, Agbenyegah (2019) noted that extrinsic rewards including merit pay, bonuses, wages and salaries, contribute to high performance.

Extrinsic rewards can serve as motivators for employees by offering them something valuable in return for their efforts. Shaikh, Pathan and Khoso (2018) revealed that when employees are clearly communicated and become aware of the rewards tied to specific performance goals, their efforts tend to align with those goals hence attainment of certain targets that can enhance performance. But, extrinsic rewards can stifle creativity, innovation and consistent performance, especially when the employees focus a lot on rewards gained. Noorazem, Sabri and Nazir (2021) share that equity and fair and transparent distribution of the extrinsic rewards can motivate, increase appreciation and performance outputs of the employees. Effectiveness of extrinsic rewards application in organization depends on how they are implemented, the organizational structure and culture as a means of sustaining high employee satisfaction and performance.

Extrinsic rewards are things that employees in an organization get for what they do and it is in tangible form. Mule (2020) shared that managers in many organizations often use this type of reward as a motivational factor to encourage employees to work harder and achieve their goals. The rewards are external to one's action and typically in monetary form such as bonuses, pay rise and promotions. It can also include corporate gifts with items like branded pens, notebooks, calendar and shopping voucher or seasonal holidays. Muyela and Kamaara (2021) noted that

profit-sharing-plans are another effective means of reward higher performers, since the incentive is directly linked to profits of the company. So, the employees enjoy a portion of the company's earnings. When used correctly, extrinsic reward is an effective tool for motivating people to attain their goals.

The reward is tied to a specific goal and hence pushes the employees to achieve the goal and later earn the reward. The rewards motivate the behavior of employees and act as an incentive to behave in a specified manner, but this also means that employees may be just acting, will persevere in a boring and unfulfilling job and do the bare minimum, as long as they meet the threshold for getting the reward. Focusing on rewards can lead to unethical behavior, focusing on the results and not process and unhealthy focus on money (Cheboi, 2014). The human resource managers should cautious and carefully in planning and implementing of any reward scheme, and monitor it to deliver on the mandate of the organization. It is important that the extrinsic rewards serve as a motivational tool for encouraging positive behavior and pushing employees to deliver on objectives.

1.1.1 Employee Performance

Employee performance is defined as how well a person executes work assignments and responsibilities (Taba, 2018). It is also viewed as completion of tasks, behavior/conduct at the workplace and handling of the assignments and duties. In most organizations, employee performance is measured in a quarterly or annually basis based on attainment of certain key parameters. The performance measurement informs the management of the organization on decision making on elements such as promotion, awards, retention or expulsion from the organization. Ekhayemhe and Oguzie (2018) noted on four types of employee performance, namely quality of work in terms of competence, thoroughness and accuracy; second is quantity of work measured as production levels, time management, units produced and capacity to meet set deadlines; the third is on job knowledge as based on skills and capacity to understand the job-related features and lastly working relations as viewed in terms of capacity to communicate and work with others.

When employees fulfill their work duties and roles in a competent manner, it signals and helps the management to differentiate between employee one and others, as based on performance outcomes (Tovmasyan & Minasyan, 2020). It is therefore, important for the leadership and management in the organization to constant monitor and frequently evaluating performance of employees. This will paint a picture of how the organization is doing as broken down to the contribution of each department, working area, employee working team and down to individual employees' contribution. Employee performance measurement, according to Rugami, Wambua and Mwatha (2016), it can be done using different performance review methods. This includes 360-degree feedback method, where the managers seek views, assessment and feedback from team members and supervisors and provides a well-rounder outlook of employee performance. It is also done through objective-based performance measure where managers work with individual employee to set goals, deadlines and expectations, such that performance is assessed against the goals. Others are ranked performance scales ranging from 1-5 or 1-10 or on percentage level for each specific task and last employee performance can be done through self-evaluations. The importance is to assess if the employee is meeting goals and on the pathway towards attaining that.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Government ministries record poor performance as reported by the general public from the services they receive. Performance and service quality ratings are low as linked to slow timeliness from request to delivery of the service, quality, variety and value of products and services (Muyela & Kamaara, 2021). Some efforts to improve service and products delivered by the Kenyan government include performance contracting, performance reviews and appraisals with dismal results. Korir and Kipkebut (2016) noted that many public servants are demoralized and unsatisfied with their work environment, reward system and benefits enjoy. This has also led to increased staff turnover and poaching of talented staff to private entities. Therefore, it raises the question on what can be done to improve employee performance in government ministries and department. Matolo, Iravo and Waititu (2019) noted that reward management programs improved employee performance, retention rates, satisfaction and motivation at technical learning institutions in Kenya. This study sets out to assess if specifically extrinsic rewards will produce the same results in terms of high employee performance in the state department for basic education.

Organizations face the problem of deciding the right reward scheme that fits the needs of the employees and the organization. Noorazem, Sabri and Nazir (2021) noted that a poor and improper reward scheme will lead to low employee morale, dissatisfaction with work, high turnover rates, unproductivity, wastage and loss of resources that negatively affect employee. Lipuku, Sang and Rop (2022) mentioned that initiatives, strategies and systems that focus on compensation and employee support have failed to improve employee satisfaction levels and employee performance. While Okoli, Okoli and Nuel-Okoli (2020) found that inadequate reward scheme is an act of injustice and causes low staff morale and high turnover rates that negatively affects individual employee performance. At the same time, when the effort is not proportionate to rewards, then the reward becomes a cause for low performance

1.2 Objective

This article's main focus is establishing influence of extrinsic rewards on employee performance

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Review

Expectancy Theory

The theory was formulated by Vroom (1964), proposing that a person will behave in a certain manner based on what they expect to gain. As such, the motivation for the chosen behavior lies on the desirability of the expected outcome. The theory is based on cognitive or mental processes that influence the choice and explains the mental processes that each individual undertakes when making a choice on conduct. According to Chiang and Jang (2008) the theory emphasizes the need for organizations to link rewards to performance, such that the rewards will induce choice of conduct and behaviors of the employees.

The expectancy theory describes the reasoning behind people choosing one behavior over another one. Thus, a person is driven to choose a specific behavior because there is positive relationship between the efforts expended and performance. For positive performance, an individual will behave in a manner to enhance the performance and obtain the desirable reward. The decision-

making process entail estimating effort needed to get the expected rewards. Thus, according to Vroom (1964) expectation is based on valence, expectation and instrumentality. But, Averbek (2010) noted that the theory was limited since it seemed idealistic based on perception that there is high degree of correlation between rewards and performance. In many organizations rewards are not directly correlated to performance. It is also difficult to assign similar values for the individual and that of the organization, since every person has different values (Lloyd & Mertens, 2018).

This theory was applied in studies done by Özaslan and Özaslan (2022) who noted that teachers in Turkey lacked external rewards which negatively affected motivation levels and positive feelings with the work assignments. Chopra (2019) shared that use of artificial intelligence by Indian shoppers was done due to expectations that the AI tool is reliable, trust-worthy and easy to use. Therefore, this theory explains how best to influence behavior of employees in the state department for basic education. The leadership at the state department should offer extrinsic rewards to its employees as a means of influencing their behavior and conduct that will reflect positively on their performance outcome. When these employees expect the extrinsic rewards will expend effort and behave accordingly in a manner to perform well and reap the rewards. Hence, the expectancy theory explains how extrinsic rewards including salary, salary increment, bonus pay and monetary gifts can influence employees to work hard and impact positively on individual employee performance.

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

Chantal, Manyange and Asuman (2022) conducted a study on how extrinsic rewards and related to employee performance in Shyogwe Diocese, Rwanda. The study focus was on use of extrinsic rewards to improve employee performance at Shyogwe Diocese. The study collected primary data from questionnaires and interview guide. The data was in quantitative and qualitative nature and it was analyzed through correlation, regression and content means. Findings showed that extrinsic rewards including paying of monthly salaries, bonus pay, giving house allowance or accommodation at the workplace, paid annual leave, insurance policy and pension schemes that have been critical in improving employee performance. The study created contextual gap since its background setting was in religious organizations in Shyogwe Diocese in Rwanda.

Miah and Hafit (2021) study was on link between extrinsic rewards and employee performance as mediated by job satisfaction of the employee. The study was done in the food and beverage industry in Malaysia and the study respondents included 60 employees of Sunway City. Quantitative and qualitative research methods were deployed and data collection was done using open-ended questionnaires. The findings revealed that extrinsic rewards had weak, positive and significant association with job satisfaction that improved employee performance in the food and beverage industries. The results also showed that job satisfaction had no significant association with employee and there was no influence of job satisfaction in the relationship between extrinsic rewards and employee performance. There were conceptual gap since extrinsic rewards was not directly linked to employee performance because of the mediating effect of job satisfaction. Contextual gap was due to the study background being in the food and beverage industry in Malaysia.

Khan, Shahid, Nawab and Wali (2013) study was on influence of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards on employee performance in the bank sector in Pakistan. The study was based on theoretical foundation of the Herzberg's two factor theory on employees job satisfaction and job performance as reflected in the overall performance of commercial banks. The researchers collected data using Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ) survey and 165 bank employees filled and returned the tool. Descriptive and inferential statistics was conducted using SPSS v.16 and found that satisfaction of bank employees was satisfactory. The study concluded that intrinsic and extrinsic rewards increase overall job satisfaction and performance of employees. Contextual gaps were created as the study was done in Pakistan and the banking sector and conceptually, both reward types were analyzed.

Ali, Edwin and Tirimba (2015) study was on extrinsic rewards and employee satisfaction, at a case of Somtel Company in Somaliland. The study focus was on how salaries, bonuses, commission and working condition affect employee satisfaction. The study was anchored on equity, affective-event and job characteristics theory and collected data from a sample of 56 employees using semi-structured questionnaires. After conducting qualitative and quantitative data analysis, the results indicated that salaries, bonus payment, ordinary commission and working conditions have a positive relationship with performance. It was concluded that there is presence of positive

association between extrinsic rewards and employees satisfaction. As a case study, the application of findings may be limited, thus the study created methodological gaps.

Kayode and Yarie (2016) conducted a research on extrinsic rewards and performance of non-teaching staff in Federal College of Education Zaria in the five-year period from 2005 to 2010. The study seeks answers on how human resource managers can motivate employees in the quest to improve performance and greater productivity. The data was collected from surveys done and covered the non-teaching staff at the college and the data was analyzed using simple frequency count, percentages and deviation of responses. The results indicate that financial related rewards constitute the vital motivator among the staff and contributed to high performance. The paper concludes that an extrinsic reward is a vital tool for achieving intrinsic motivation among the survey group to achieve higher performance. The gap was in context as it covered non-teaching staffs only and the background was in Nigeria.

Milka, Michael and Tanui (2015) conducted a study on the effect of extrinsic motivation on employee performance in medium-class hotels in Kisumu City-Kenya. Specifically, extrinsic motivational rewards include elements such as working conditions, incentives and interpersonal relations and how they affect employee performance. The study respondents included employees in the medium-class hotels in Kisumu City. Questionnaires were used to collect data that was quantitative in nature and later analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics (Pearson product moment and multiple regression. The findings showed that no single element of extrinsic motivational reward affected employee performance and hence the need for extrinsic motivational reward elements. The study concluded that combined elements of extrinsic motivational rewards improve employee performance. Contextual gaps were created since the focus was in the hotel sector and medium-sized hotels in Kisumu City.

Umar (2012) research was on effect of wages, motivation and job satisfaction on worker performance in manufacturing industries in Makassar, Indonesia. The study focused on assessing effect of wages and employee motivation and job satisfaction; and the effect of work motivation, job satisfaction and wages and employee performance within the manufacturing firms in Indonesia. Data was collected from executive operational employees in 20 manufacturing industries and 300 workers who were randomly sampled to participate in the study. Through

structural equation modeling, the study found that wages, work motivation and job satisfaction significantly affected employee performance. In addition, job satisfaction affected motivation and performance. The study created conceptual gaps since wages was not directly linked to performance and the study context was in Indonesia and its manufacturing industry.

Kanzunnudin (2007) researched on wages and supervision and effects on employee productivity. This was a case study of PT Tonga in Zenith District. The focus was examining wages and supervision on employee productivity through the use of standard ordinary least square method. The results observed that wages and supervision significantly influenced productivity. The results showed that supervision had stronger influence to productivity when compared to wages. The study created methodological gaps since it was a case study and it may limit application of the findings. The study also created contextual gaps since it was done in Tonga, Zenith District, and there is need to localize the study to Kenyan background.

Agburu (2012) conducted a research on recent trends on wage and salary administration in Nigeria through synopsis of theoretical and empirical challenges. The study noted that the question of administration of wages and salary in Nigeria faces unresolved issues and controversies from politico-administrative setup. Focus has been on sorting issues of basic pay, labor costs, production costs, cost of living and compensation for work done. The research adopted cross-sectional survey method and using non-parametric methods reviewed past studies. The findings showed that lags on labor/employee pay and productivity and large income differentials between government employees and others in the same market. The study created conceptual gaps since wages and salaries was not linked to employee performance and contextual gaps since it was done in the Nigeria's public service.

Hameed, Ramzan, Zubair, Ali and Arslan (2014) study was on compensation impact on employee performance in the banking sector in Pakistan. The researchers collected data using questionnaires from employees of the different bank on compensation in terms of salary, rewards and indirect compensation and how it affects employee performance. Analytical and descriptive analysis was conducted and findings revealed that compensation positively impacted employee performance but the association was moderate. The study created contextual gaps since it covered only banking sector in Pakistan and hence the need for research on other sectors and in other region.

3.0 Methodology

This study conducted a desk review of extrinsic rewards and employee performance. The reviews were based on adopted descriptive research design that allowed the researcher to describe the perspective, research methods, data and its analysis, findings and drawn conclusions. Descriptive research design allowed the researcher to report on the reviewed articles. Purposively sampling was done by focusing only on the published and peer reviewed articles found on different online platforms. The desk review focused on past literature on the global context, regional and local perspective on how extrinsic rewards influences performance of the employees. The review also consisted of assessing the different extrinsic reward elements and its frequency in use by the different authors. The secondary data was collected and analyzed through context format and findings shared. The findings from the review was analyzed and conclusions drawn that would inform managerial practice, policy and theory.

4.0 Findings and Conclusions

From the literature reviewed and assessment of published and peer-reviewed articles, this study found that extrinsic rewards had positive effects to employee performance that also reflected positively on overall organization performance. The extrinsic rewards included salary, salary pay rise, bonuses and monetary gifts as they affect employee performance. We can therefore conclude that extrinsic rewards influenced the performance outcomes of employees of an organization. The extrinsic rewards with individual constructs of salary and salary increment improved employee performance and the studies concluded that extrinsic rewards influence employee performance. Bonuses were found to improve employee performance and hence conclusions are that bonuses used in organizations lead to improved employee performance. On monetary gifts, the reviewed

studies showed that it influenced employee performance and thus concluded that monetary gifts improve employee performance in organizations.

5.0 Recommendations

The theoretical, empirical reviews and desk review of articles indicate that extrinsic rewards improve performance of employees in terms of delivering quality, timely and responsive services as per the work task assignment and demands of the general public. Therefore, this article makes the following recommendations to the organizations to develop a fair, equitable and just reward scheme that will motivate and lift the morale of the employees, resulting in them performing highly. The extrinsic reward offered in the organization should be factual and transparent where every employee is aware that this performance level earns this amount of rewards. The recommendations for policy makers is formulation of laws and regulations that will guide industry players in awarding employees who perform highly based on specific structure and format. The human resource department and staffs should follow the guidelines in fairly awarding extrinsic rewards in terms of increased salaries, monetary gifts and performance only to high performers. The rewards should be given in an open and transparent manner such that it becomes a motivating factor. To the academic world, these are recommendations for researchers and authors, to expand literature by focusing on private and profit-making organizations to assess how extrinsic rewards influence employee performance. These researchers can also consider other reward types such as promotions, recognition, promotions and others as they impact employee performance. Researchers should delve deeper in link between rewards and performance of employees in different organizational type, sector and industry.

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